

Soft Computing Based Battery Charger

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Abstract : This paper proposes soft computing technique called Deterministic Particle Swarm Optimization (DPSO) is used to track the maximum power in the condition of partial shading condition of Photo Voltaic (PV) system. Particles moves based on environmental condition and maximum power of PV to be tracked which is used to charge the battery backup. To estimate the results of this paper, MATLAB software is used.

Keywords : DPSO, Partial shading condition, P&O, PV,Battery

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